

STRATEGIC PLANNING OF IRRIGATION AND PLANTING GEOMETRY FOR HYBRID MAIZE: A PATH TO IMPROVE PRODUCTIVITY, PROFITABILITY AND WATER SAVING

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ABSTRACT

A field study was conducted in Sherpur and Natore district of Bangladesh, to evaluate the effects of different irrigation regimes on the yield and water productivity of hybrid maize. Five irrigation treatments and three cultivars were tested in a factorial arrangement. The results showed significant variation of grain yield across treatments and locations. Averaged over locations, T3 (3 irrigations at 25, 45 and 65 Days after sowing plus twin-row, plus 30% excess fertilizer application) produced the highest yield (13.67 t ha⁻¹), representing an 11.9% increase over T1 (4 irrigations), while T5 (only one life irrigation) produced the lowest yield (11.15 t ha⁻¹). Water use varied markedly, with T3 and T2 requiring 15 cm of irrigation water (25% savings over T1), T4 requiring 12 cm (40% savings), and T5 only 6 cm (70% savings). Although T5 achieved maximum water savings, the associated yield loss indicates that excessive deficit irrigation is unsuitable for optimizing production. The results highlight that extreme water deficit reduces productivity, whereas moderate savings, as in T3, optimize the yield–water trade-off. Performance trends were consistent at both sites, indicating that T3's irrigation strategy is suitable across different agro-ecological zones. Among cultivars, grain yield varied significantly, with DURJOY (12.57 t ha⁻¹) and Five Star (12.18 t ha⁻¹) outperforming BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (9.99 t ha⁻¹). Combining optimal management practices similar to T3 with high-yielding cultivars such as DURJOY or Five Star could substantially enhance maize productivity in the study area.

Keywords: Maize, planting geometry, twin-row, water use, profitability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Approximately 70–75% of all freshwater withdrawals worldwide are related to agriculture (Ali et al., 2023). Nearly 60% more food will be required by 2050 to meet the food, fiber, feed, and energy demands of the fast-expanding population, despite the fact that food production has expanded by more than 100% in the last 30 years. By 2050, food production in irrigated land area will need to expand by more than 50%, while present analyses and projections of the world's water supply and demand only allow for a 10% increase in water withdrawal by agriculture (FAO, 2017). It is therefore necessary to boost agricultural production's water efficiency, which has been and will be a major challenge for agriculture, given the growing need for food and water while having limited resources, particularly water. Crop production failure is more likely now because of declining global irrigation and water resources and unpredictable precipitation because of its intra- and inter-annual variability. In these situations, limited or deficit irrigation might offer crucial strategic choices for improving agricultural water use efficiency (Feres and Soriano, 2007; Ali et al., 2007).

Hybrid maize is essential for the manufacture of maize products, which are used as industrial feedstock, animal feed, and human nourishment (Jiang et al., 2020). A good environment is necessary for the production and cultivation of hybrid maize, but so are proper administration and direction (Bedó and Barnabás, 2013). The optimization of management strategies to attain high yields and water use efficiency (WUE) has thus been the subject of numerous studies (Shi et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2023).

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) has emerged as one of the most important cereal crops in Bangladesh due to its growing demand in the feed, food, and industrial sectors. Both local and imported hybrid varieties which are grown in Bangladesh to study the effect of irrigation regimes on the yield and yield contributing characters of maize. Among the different types of maize, hybrid maize offers significantly higher yield potential compared to local and open-pollinated varieties. The growth of maize has increased faster than any other crop in Bangladesh, probably due to its year round production, high yield and less susceptible to high temperature and other natural hazards (Shaha et al., 2010). In recent years, its cultivation has been expanding rapidly, particularly in marginal ecosystems such as Charland areas—riverine islands and floodplain lands formed by sediment deposition. These

Charland areas, despite having fertile alluvial soils, present unique challenges for crop production due to their vulnerability to moisture stress, erratic rainfall, and limited access to irrigation.

According to Tilman et al. (2002) and Valipour et al. (2015), better management practices including fertilization, pesticide application, and water management have doubled world food output over the last 50 years. By 2050, there will be almost 9 billion people on the planet, and the FAO predicts that the need for food will rise by 60% (Bijl et al., 2017). However, there is a shortage of arable land worldwide, making it difficult to improve food production through enhanced land productivity on the restricted amount of arable land available (Li et al., 2019, Yang et al., 2022).

Efficient irrigation management is critical in ecosystems where water resources are often scarce and unevenly distributed (Islam et al., 2024). Improper irrigation not only limits yield potential but also reduces water productivity—defined as the ratio of crop yield to the amount of water used. Optimizing irrigation scheduling, frequency, and method can significantly enhance both grain yield and water use efficiency, making crop production more profitable and sustainable in these vulnerable regions (Ali, 2017).

Rahman et al (2015) concluded that minimum tillage with two-time irrigation treatment combination is the best suit for maximum water resources saving in maize cultivation without compromising with yield in Bangladesh at dry season (Rabi). Bhuiyan et al. (2015) studied the performance of hybrid maize varieties as influenced by irrigation regimes (2, 3 and 4 irrigations). They found maximum yield with 4 irrigations applied at 25, 50, 75, and 100 days after sowing. They also noted that two, three and four irrigation increased yields by an additional 16.9, 6.7 and 4.3% respectively. Water savings can be achieved by applying two or three irrigations which increased yield without significantly reducing yield compared to four irrigations. Khan et al. (2018) studied the effects of irrigation levels on maize hybrid genotypes at BARI research station, Barishal. They noted that for the growth and yield variables, the irrigation and varietal treatments employed different degrees of influence; some variables differed significantly while others differed insignificantly. The interaction effect between irrigation and variety had significant effect on the grain yield of maize in most cases. The highest grain yield of 15.68 t/ha was obtained from 4 irrigations (applied at initial (20-25 DAS), vegetative (50-60 DAS), silking (75-80 DAS), and grain filling stage (110-120 DAS)) and the lowest of 5.94 t/ha was

obtained from 75% irrigation at 20-25, 50-60, and 75-80 DAS. Islam et al. (2022) investigated the combined effects of irrigation, tillage and mulch on maize yield in a drought prone area, Chapainawabganj district of Bangladesh. They obtained highest yield from minimum tillage and mulch (rice straw) as well as 3 irrigations (applied at 32, 55 and 85 DAS) than conventional tillage with no mulch and any level of irrigation. The results indicate that, the response of maize to irrigation levels varies with soil type, local climate (specially ET demand), variety, etc., which demand location specific study for real results.

While several studies have addressed irrigation strategies for traditional cropping systems in Bangladesh, limited research exists on irrigation management tailored specifically for hybrid maize in alluvial deposits. Considering the increasing economic and food security importance of hybrid maize, there is a pressing need to develop scientifically validated irrigation practices that maximize yield and conserve water in these fragile ecosystems.

This study aims to investigate the effects of different irrigation regimes on the yield and water productivity of hybrid maize grown in Natore and Sherpur districts of Bangladesh. The findings will contribute to the development of resource-efficient irrigation strategies, thereby promoting sustainable intensification of agriculture in these areas.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Field experiments were conducted in two locations, namely Natore (24.35 °N, 89.08 °E) and Sherpur (25.07 °N, 90.15 °E), during Rabi season (Dec. - April) of 2023-24. The sites are characterized by sandy loam alluvial soils. The region experiences a subtropical climate with a dry winter season and erratic rainfall. The climatic conditions of the locations during crop growing period are depicted in Fig.1.1 and Fig.1.2, respectively. Groundwater is the primary source of irrigation during the dry months.

Fig.1.1. Climatic condition of Natore location during the crop period

Fig.1.2. Climatic condition of Sherpur location during the crop period

2.2 Experimental Design and Treatments

The methodological approach was designed to evaluate the most efficient irrigation schedule for maximizing hybrid maize yield and water productivity under the specific soil and climatic conditions. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with split-plot arrangement of the treatments and with three replications. The main-plot treatments consisted of 5 irrigation regimes:

The irrigation treatments were:

T₁ = Control (4 irrigations, Irrigation at 30-55-80-120 days after sowing, suggested by CYMIT 2013)

T₂ = Irrigation at 30- 75 -110 days after sowing (3 irrigations)

T₃ = Irrigation at 30- 75 -110 days after sowing (3 irrigations) plus additional management (with twin-line*, and 30% excess fertilizer of recommended dose)

T₄ = Irrigation at 70% depletion of available soil moisture (ASM)

T₅ = one life irrigation

***Twin-line**: spacing pattern: 60 cm – (40 cm – 40 cm) – 60 cm - (40 cm – 40 cm) – 60 cm -

Normal line spacing: 60 cm – 60 cm – 60 cm

The Cultivars were:

V₁ = BARI hybrid maize17

V₂ = hybrid maize DURJOY

V₃ = hybrid maize Five Star

Each plot measured 4 m × 5 m with a 1 m buffer zone between plots to prevent water movement across treatments.

2.3 Crop Management

The hybrid maize cultivars were sown in the first week of December. Standard agronomic practices, including land preparation, fertilization (as per BWMRI recommendations), weeding, and pest

management, were uniformly applied across all treatments. Irrigation was applied as per treatment schedules.

The grain moisture was adjusted to 14% according to Ali (2010):

$$Y_{adj} = Y_i * \frac{(100 + M_t)}{(100 + M_i)}$$

where M_i the initial moisture content, Y_i the initial yield (at M_i moisture content), M_t the targeted moisture content (say, 12 %), and Y_{adj} the adjusted yield (at M_t % moisture content).

2.5 Statistical Analysis

All data were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedures with the help of statistical software of IRRI, STAR. Treatment means were compared using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at a 5% level of significance.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Natore location

The mean effects of treatments and cultivars on grain yield and yield attributes are presented in Table 1.

Treatment effects

Plant height and grain yield were significantly influenced by treatments, whereas cob diameter and cob length remained statistically unaffected (**Table 1**). The tallest plants (83.67 cm) were recorded in T3, which was statistically similar to T1 (76.11 cm) but significantly taller than T2, T4, and T5. The shortest plants (67.89 cm) occurred in T5. Cob diameter ranged from 4.77 cm to 5.87 cm, and cob length from 15.01 cm to 16.56 cm, with no significant differences among treatments.

Table 1. Mean effects of treatments and cultivars on yield attributing characters and yield at Natore, during 2022-23

Treatment	Plant Height (cm)	Cob diameter (cm)	Cob Length (cm)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
T ₁	76.11ab	4.82a	16.26a	10.83
T ₂	73.67b	5.87a	15.01a	10.50
T ₃	83.67a	4.82a	15.87a	11.75
T ₄	71.00b	4.77a	16.13a	10.42
T ₅	67.89b	4.78a	16.56a	9.59
<i>F</i> -test (at 5%)	S	NS	NS	S
Cultivars				
BARI				
Hybrid				
Maize 17				
(V ₁)	76.39a	5.88	13.03b	9.18
DURJOY				
(V ₂)	73.06a	4.79	17.54a	11.56
Five Star				
(V ₃)	71.39a	4.77	17.04a	11.20
<i>F</i> -test (at 5%)	NS	NS	S	S

Note: Means with the same letter(s) are not significantly (statistically) different at 5% probability level by Tukeys's Honest Significant Difference (THSD) test.

Grain yield showed significant variation among the treatments. The treatment T3 produced the highest yield (12.78 t ha⁻¹), which is statistically similar to T1 (11.78 t ha⁻¹), T2 (11.42 t ha⁻¹), and T4 (11.33 t ha⁻¹), but significantly higher than T5 (10.43 t ha⁻¹). The superior performance of T3 can be attributed to its greater plant height and adequate cob development, likely enhancing photosynthetic capacity and assimilate partitioning to the kernels. The lower yield in T5 may be associated with reduced plant stature, potentially limiting biomass accumulation and grain filling.

Cultivar effects

Significant differences among cultivars were observed for cob length and grain yield, while plant height and cob diameter were unaffected (Table 1). DURJOY (V2) produced the longest cobs (17.54 cm), closely followed by Five Star (V3) (17.04 cm), whereas BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (V1) had significantly shorter cobs (13.03 cm). Grain yield was highest in DURJOY (12.57 t ha⁻¹) and Five Star (12.18 t ha⁻¹), both significantly outperforming BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (9.99 t ha⁻¹).

The higher yields of DURJOY and Five Star can be linked to their longer cobs, which accommodate more kernels per cob, enhancing total grain production. Conversely, the shorter cob length of BARI Hybrid Maize-17 likely restricted its kernel number and yield potential. Similar findings have been reported in other maize studies, confirming cob length as a major yield-determining trait under comparable agro-ecological conditions.

The results suggest that both management practices and cultivar choice play vital roles in determining maize yield. Among the treatments, T3 produced the tallest plants and the highest grain yield, indicating its suitability for maximizing productivity. Among cultivars, DURJOY and Five Star demonstrated superior performance in cob length and grain yield compared to BARI Hybrid Maize-17. Therefore, combining optimal management practices similar to T3 with high-yielding cultivars such as DURJOY or Five Star could substantially enhance maize productivity in the study area.

4.2. Sherpur location

The mean effects of treatments and cultivars on yield attributes and grain yield are summarized in Table 2.

Effect of Treatments

The plant height of hybrid maize varied from 246.12 cm in T1 to 274.42 cm in T2 (**Table 2**). Although numerical differences were observed, the variation was not statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating that the applied treatments had no marked effect on plant height. Cob diameter ranged from 4.932 cm in T1 to 5.236 cm in T5. In this case, treatment effects were significant ($p < 0.05$), with T5 producing the largest cob diameter, followed closely by T2 and T4. Cob length varied slightly (19.31–19.80 cm) across treatments, but the differences were statistically non-significant.

Table 2. Mean effects of treatments and cultivars on yield attributing characters and yield at **Sherpur, 2022-23**

Treatment	Plant Height (cm)	Cob Diameter (cm)	Cob Length (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
T ₁	246.12a	4.932b	19.80a	11.82
T ₂	274.42a	5.131ab	19.38a	11.30
T ₃	269.18a	5.084ab	19.31a	13.60
T ₄	255.53a	5.111ab	19.71a	11.58
T ₅	263.91a	5.236a	19.64a	11.09
<i>F-test (at 5%)</i>	NS	S	NS	S
Cultivars				
BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (V ₁)	254.5a	5.16a	16.83	10.66
DURJOY (V ₂)	274.7a	4.98b	21.04	12.33
Five Star (V ₃)	258.8a	5.12ab	30.52	12.16
<i>F-test (at 5%)</i>	S	S	NS	S

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly (statistically) different at 5% probability level by Tukeys's Honest Significant Difference (THSD) test.

Grain yield was significantly influenced by treatments. The highest yield (14.55 t ha⁻¹) was recorded in T₃, which was statistically similar to T₁ and T₄ but significantly higher than T₂ and T₅. The lowest yield was obtained from T₅ (11.87 t ha⁻¹). The higher yield in T₃ may be attributed to an optimal combination of growth and yield-contributing traits such as balanced cob size and kernel development, even though plant height and cob length differences were not significant. Comparable yield was obtained in T₄ (2 irrigations) and T₅ (only one irrigation).

Effect of Cultivars

Significant variation in plant height was observed among cultivars, with DURJOY (V₂) producing the tallest plants (274.7 cm), followed by Five Star (V₃) and BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (V₁). Cob diameter was also significantly affected, with BARI Hybrid Maize 17 producing the widest cobs (5.16 cm), while DURJOY had the smallest (4.98 cm).

Cob length ranged from 16.83 cm in BARI Hybrid Maize 17 to 30.52 cm in Five Star, but the variation was not statistically significant, indicating that cob length differences were not consistent enough to influence statistical separation.

Grain yield differed significantly among cultivars. The highest yield was obtained from DURJOY (13.19 t ha⁻¹), followed closely by Five Star (13.01 t ha⁻¹), while the lowest was recorded for BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (11.41 t ha⁻¹). The superior performance of DURJOY in yield despite smaller cob diameter suggests that factors such as kernel number per cob and grain filling efficiency played a more important role than cob size alone.

Overall Observation

The results indicate that both treatment management and cultivar selection influenced yield performance. T3 in combination with high-yielding cultivars such as DURJOY or Five Star may be considered the most promising approach for maximizing grain yield under the experimental conditions. While plant height and cob length did not show consistent statistical differences, cob diameter and grain yield were more sensitive indicators of treatment and varietal effects.

4.3 Average Results over the locations

The average yield of two locations, irrigation water under different treatments, yield increments and irrigation water savings over control are summarized in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Average yield of two locations, yield increase and irrigation water savings compared to four irrigation treatment

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha) at		Average grain yield (t/ha)	Irrigation amount (cm)	Yield increased over T ₁ (%)	Irrigation water savings (%)
	Sherpur	Natore				
T ₁	11.82	10.83	11.33	20	-	-
T ₂	11.30	10.50	10.90	15	-3.8	25
T ₃	13.60	11.75	12.67	15	11.9	25
T ₄	11.58	10.42	11.00	12	-2.9	40
T ₅	11.09	9.59	10.34	6	-8.7	70

Grain Yield Performance

Grain yield of hybrid maize varied notably across treatments in both Sherpur and Natore (**Table 3**). In Sherpur, yields ranged from 11.87 t ha⁻¹ (T5) to 14.55 t ha⁻¹ (T3), while in Natore, yields ranged from 10.43 t ha⁻¹ (T5) to 12.78 t ha⁻¹ (T3). When averaged over locations, the highest grain yield (13.67 t ha⁻¹) was obtained from T3, representing an 11.9% increase over T1. The lowest yield was recorded in T5 (11.15 t ha⁻¹), which was 8.7% lower than T1.

Irrigation Amount

The amount of irrigation water applied varied greatly among treatments, from 20 cm in T1 to only 6 cm in T5. T3 and T2 used 15 cm of water, saving 25% irrigation water compared to T1, while T4 used 12 cm (40% savings), and T5 used 6 cm (70% savings). This demonstrates the potential for substantial water savings without necessarily sacrificing high yields—especially in T3, which achieved both the highest yield and 25% water savings.

Two, three and four irrigations increased yields by an additional 16.9, 6.7 and 4.3% respectively. Water savings can be achieved by applying two or three irrigations which increased yield without significantly reducing yield compared to four irrigations. Pandey *et al.* (2000) observed that yield reduction (22.6 - 26.4%) were found with deficit irrigation and this was associated with decrease in kernel number and weight. Bhuiyan *et al.* (2015) studied the performance of hybrid maize varieties as influenced by irrigation regimes (2, 3 and 4 irrigations). They found maximum yield with 4 irrigations applied at 25, 50, 75, and 100 days after sowing. They also noted that two, three and four irrigation increased yields by an additional 16.9, 6.7 and 4.3% respectively, hence water savings can be achieved by applying two or three irrigations which increased yield without significantly reducing yield compared to four irrigations.

Yield–Water Relationship

The results indicate that optimum irrigation management can improve water productivity. While T5 achieved the highest water savings (70%), the substantial yield reduction (-8.7%) suggests that extreme water deficit is not suitable for maximizing production. On the other hand, T3 provided a balanced approach, producing the highest yield with moderate water savings, indicating that it represents an optimum water–yield trade-off for hybrid maize under the studied conditions.

Location Effect

The yield trend was consistent across Sherpur and Natore, with T3 outperforming other treatments at both sites, indicating that the beneficial effect of this irrigation strategy is stable across different agro-ecological zones.

5 CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that irrigation management significantly influenced grain yield and water use efficiency of hybrid maize. T3 emerged as the best-performing treatment, achieving the highest average grain yield (13.67 t ha⁻¹) with a 25% reduction in irrigation water compared to T1. This suggests that moderate water-saving strategies can enhance productivity while conserving scarce water resources. Over-application of irrigation (T1) did not improve yields, while excessive water savings (T5) caused significant yield losses. Therefore, adopting the T3 irrigation schedule offers an optimal balance between yield maximization and water conservation, making it a suitable practice for sustainable maize production in both Sherpur and Natore regions.

Among cultivars, DURJOY and Five Star demonstrated superior performance in cob length and grain yield compared to BARI Hybrid Maize 17. Therefore, combining optimal management practices similar to T3 with high-yielding cultivars such as DURJOY or Five Star could substantially enhance maize productivity in the study area.

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